

ISic1478

I.Sicily inscription 1478

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

02.10.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

necropolis of la Pinita

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6823

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140521

1. Βραχί-
2. δ,α εἰμί. ²⁷Βραχύ | λ,α? (Jeffery, LSAG)²⁷.
- 3.

Edition: PHI175430

1. Βραχύ-
2. λ,α εἰμί.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644988

PHI 140521

PHI 175430

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0221a (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Arena, R. 1998. Iscrizioni greche arcaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. V. Iscrizioni di Taranto, Locri Epizefiri, Velia e Siracusa. Alessandria. At no.77

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